

ORGANIZATION OF EMERGENCY MEDICAL CARE FOR THE POPULATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article examines the organization of emergency medical care for the population in Uzbekistan in the context of modern challenges and healthcare development strategies. The authors cover key aspects of the ambulance system, including the call mechanism, team structure, methods of providing medical care at the scene and in medical facilities, and interaction with other emergency services. The article also discusses current challenges facing ambulance systems, such as increased call volumes, the need for staff development and equipment upgrades, as well as strategies to address these challenges. The authors conclude by emphasizing the importance of an efficient emergency medical services system to ensure rapid response to medical emergencies and minimize public health consequences.

Key words: organization, emergency medical care, population, personnel training, medical institutions, doctors, nurses.

The organization of emergency medical care for the population in Uzbekistan is a comprehensive system aimed at promptly responding to medical emergencies and providing quality care to victims.

1. Calling an ambulance: The population of Uzbekistan can call an ambulance using a special telephone number. Dispatchers receive calls, assess the situation and dispatch ambulance crews to the scene of the incident.
2. Emergency medical team: Ambulance teams consist of doctors, nurses and ambulance drivers. They are equipped with the necessary equipment and medicines to provide first aid at the scene of an incident and transport patients to medical facilities. An emergency medical team is a specialized group of

medical professionals who quickly respond to calls for help in medical emergencies. The ambulance crew usually includes doctors, nurses and ambulance drivers. They provide fast and effective medical care at the scene of an incident and transport patients to medical facilities for further treatment.

The responsibilities of the emergency medical team include:

- Providing first aid at the scene of an incident, including assessing the condition of victims, providing emergency medical care, applying temporary splints, performing resuscitation measures, etc.
- Transportation of victims to medical institutions, where they will be provided with further qualified medical care.
- Adhere to emergency medical services protocols and standards, and collaborate with other emergency services to effectively respond to a variety of situations.
- Maintaining and updating the necessary medical equipment and medications in ambulances.

The emergency medical team plays a key role in saving lives and providing quality medical care in critical situations, and its operational work is an integral part of the healthcare system.

3. Medical facilities: Victims are sent to medical facilities where they receive further medical care. These may be hospitals, emergency rooms or other specialized institutions. Medical institutions in Uzbekistan represent a variety of institutions designed to provide medical care to the population. These include: Hospitals and Clinics: Hospitals provide a wide range of medical services, including inpatient treatment, surgery, diagnostics and consultations with specialists in various fields of medicine. Clinics usually specialize in certain types of medical care, such as outpatient treatment, preventive examinations, dentistry, etc. Polyclinics: Polyclinics provide outpatient medical care to the population. Here patients can receive consultations from doctors of various specialties, undergo tests, receive prescriptions for medications and undergo procedures. Maternity hospitals: Maternity hospitals

provide medical care to pregnant women during pregnancy, childbirth and the postpartum period. It also offers birth preparation courses and various medical procedures. Emergency rooms: Emergency rooms are designed to provide first aid to victims in case of injuries and emergencies. It has the necessary equipment and qualified personnel to carry out emergency medical interventions. Pharmacies: Pharmacies provide the opportunity to purchase medications with or without doctor's prescriptions, as well as consultation with pharmacists on the selection and use of medications. These medical institutions form the basis of the healthcare system of Uzbekistan and provide the population with high-quality and affordable medical care.

4. Coordination with other services: Emergency medical services works closely with other emergency services, such as fire and police, to effectively respond to medical emergencies.
5. Education and training of personnel: Emergency physicians and nurses undergo special training and regularly undergo advanced training courses to effectively respond to various situations and provide a high level of medical care. This system ensures prompt and professional assistance to victims in the event of medical emergencies and helps preserve the health and life of citizens of Uzbekistan.

Education and training of personnel in the healthcare system of Uzbekistan plays a key role in providing quality medical care to the population. Some of the main aspects of staff education and training include:

1. Medical educational institutions: Uzbekistan has specialized medical universities and medical colleges, where future medical workers receive academic education and practical training. Training includes theoretical courses, practical training and internships in medical institutions.
2. Advanced training courses: Advanced training and professional retraining courses are regularly conducted for current medical personnel. These courses

- cover various aspects of medical practice, new diagnostic and treatment methods, and updates in health care legislation and standards.
3. Simulation training: Simulation training and simulators are used for practical training of medical personnel for real situations. This allows clinicians to learn how to respond to different medical scenarios without putting patients at risk.
 4. Training in specialized programs: For medical personnel working in certain areas of health care, such as emergency care, anesthesiology, resuscitation and others, specialized training and certification programs are provided.
 5. Online learning and electronic resources: In modern conditions, more and more attention is paid to online learning and access to electronic resources. This allows medical staff to receive updated information and training at a convenient time and place.
 6. Staff education and training is a continuous process that enables healthcare staff to maintain a high level of professionalism, cope with new challenges in healthcare and provide quality patient care.

Conclusion. In the context of constantly changing healthcare, the organization of medical emergency services for the population of Uzbekistan plays an important role in providing fast and high-quality medical care in emergency situations. Despite the progress made, the EMS system still has some challenges to overcome, such as increasing the number of calls, ensuring sufficient education and training of personnel, and updating equipment and technology. The effective functioning of the emergency medical services system requires the joint efforts of government, healthcare, educational institutions and the public. It is necessary to continue to invest in staff education and training, improve coordination with other emergency services and upgrade equipment to ensure a high level of medical care in all circumstances. The emergency medical care system of Uzbekistan is an integral part of the country's healthcare system and plays an important role in maintaining the health and well-being of the population. The implementation of effective strategies

to improve the performance of the ambulance system will ensure a rapid response to medical emergencies and improve the quality of life of citizens of Uzbekistan.

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